

A method for the reliable and reproducible precipitation of phase pure high Ca/Si ratio (>1.5) synthetic calcium silicate hydrates (C—S—H)

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ABSTRACT

Various methods have been developed to synthesize C—S—H; however, these methods have only allowed for the successful production of pure-phase C—S—H with Ca:Si of 1.5 or less. Attempts to form higher Ca:Si ratios by these methods gives C—S—H (Ca:Si 1.5 or less) in the presence of Ca(OH)₂. This paper focuses on a reliable method to produce single-phase C—S—H with Ca:Si molar ratios between 1 and 2. Reactant concentrations, temperature, pH, and mixing conditions are carefully controlled to ensure homogeneous precipitation of C—S—H. Guidelines on collection, drying, storage, and handling are also described.

1. Introduction

Calcium silicate hydrate, CaO-SiO₂-H₂O, or C—S—H, is the glue of Portland cement. Formed during the hydration of alite and belite, which together make up about 70–80% of Portland cement, C—S—H is the chief contributor to early-age strength and comprises around 50% of the solid volume of hardened cement paste [1]. With its strength and high specific surface area, applications of C—S—H range from construction to more biological applications [2–4].

C—S—H has a variable stoichiometry and water content. At early ages, the C—S—H in hydrated Portland cements has Ca:Si molar ratios between 1.7 and 2. It is possible to obtain C—S—H at a wide range of Ca:Si molar ratios from 0.7 to over 2, which is related to concentrations of Ca and Si in solution and the local pH [5–7].

Preparation of synthetic, single-phase C—S—H allows characterization of the main hydration phase without the presence of additional minerals. In work done over the past two decades, C—S—H has been synthesized in different ways to study solubility [8], structure and morphology [6,9,10], compressive strength [2], and bioactivity and setting [11,12]. Most commonly, C—S—H has been synthesized by combining CaO or Ca(OH)₂ with a reactive silica and reacting for three to ten months [2,8,9,13–19]. However, this synthesis route has been shown to only, reliably, produce single-phase C—S—H at Ca:Si molar ratios of 1.5 or below. Double decomposition of sodium silicate with a calcium salt has also been used to make synthetic C—S—H at a wide range of Ca:Si molar ratios, described in work done by Chen et al. and Lodeiro et al. [8,20]. Samples with nominal Ca:Si of up to 1.9 were synthesized, but the samples are reported to have formed in conjunction

with portlandite, and corrected Ca:Si ratios are not reported.

Kumar et al. succeeded in producing pure, single-phase C—S—H at a Ca:Si of 2 using a method which combines direct double decomposition and dropwise precipitation [7]. The experimental data obtained from this high Ca:Si C—S—H allowed an atomistic level model to be constructed that accounts for the full range of Ca:Si molar ratios. However, this synthesis method has proven to be difficult to replicate, and much like the other methods, targeting higher Ca:Si ratios has often resulted in producing C—S—H in conjunction with Ca(OH)₂ (portlandite), and/or CaCO₃ (carbonates).

Thermodynamic and kinetic modelling indicates that the Ca:Si of C—S—H produced in the method of Kumar et al. depends on the pH of the environment, and from kinetic modelling portlandite is never oversaturated in the media as long as care is taken to maintain proper mixing throughout the synthesis [7,21]. Despite this, we find in practice that portlandite and carbonates may form.

Much like any family recipe, there are one or two minor ingredients or tricks that make all the difference between high-quality, pure C—S—H and a mixed, poor-quality C—S—H. In this work, we describe a reproducible protocol for pure, single-phase, synthetic C—S—H with Ca:Si molar ratios from 1 to 2 based on the dropwise precipitation method and GEMS thermodynamic modelling [22,23]. The samples were characterized with X-ray diffraction (XRD), thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), X-ray fluorescence (XRF), and inductively coupled plasma spectrometry (ICP-OES) with the goal of defining the steps needed to produce pure C—S—H and determining which parameters affect the formation of secondary phases. To prevent the formation of impurities during collection, drying, storage, and handling; additional guidelines

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are provided.

2. Characterization methods

X-ray powder diffraction was carried out by a PANalytical X'pert X-ray diffractometer with an X'celerator detector with double bounced monochromatic $\text{CuK}\alpha_{1,2}$ radiation. Wet and dry C—S—H samples were prepared through the back-loading process, in which the sample holder is loaded from the rear, and were placed on a rotating sample stage. The patterns were recorded between 5° and 70° (2θ) with a fixed divergence slit of $\frac{1}{2}$ and a step size of 0.017° for 30 min. XRD was used to observe the intrinsic C—S—H peaks at 29.4 , 32.1 , and $50.1 \pm 0.1^\circ$ [24], as well as any secondary phases.

To analyze samples by TGA, dried C—S—H was heated at a rate of $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ from 30°C to 1000°C under a flow of nitrogen at $10\text{ mL}/\text{min}$. The weight losses in relation to time and temperature were recorded on a Mettler Toledo AG (TGA/SDTA851e). Portlandite and calcium carbonate amounts were analyzed using the tangent method at

temperatures between 400°C and 480°C and 600°C and 710°C , respectively, as described by Lothenbach et al. [25]. The tangent method reduces overestimation due to the continuation of water loss in C—S—H at higher temperatures.

To prepare C—S—H samples for ICP analysis, 0.013 g of freshly prepared, wet C—S—H was dissolved in 1 mL of 65% nitric acid and placed in an ultrasonic bath for 30 min . 9 mL of 0.1 M diluted aqua regia was added to each sample. The solution was placed in the ultrasonic bath for an additional 15 min , and then placed in a 50°C oven for 24 h . Desired dilutions were prepared with decarbonated water. Acidified precipitate samples exhibited maximum concentrations of Ca, Si, and Na at 200 , 100 , and $100\text{ mg}/\text{L}$, respectively.

To prepare a reaction supernatant sample for ICP, 2 mL of supernatant were acidified in 3 mL of 65% nitric acid. The solution was placed in an ultrasonic bath for 30 min . 4-fold, 10-fold, and 20-fold dilutions were made using decarbonated water. Acidified supernatant samples exhibited maximum concentrations of Ca, Si, and Na at 70 , 5 , and $2000\text{ mg}/\text{L}$, respectively.

Fig. 1. Schematic of batch reactor setup for dropwise precipitation of C—S—H [7], with slots in the lid for nitrogen purging and in-situ measurements.

All diluted samples were stored in 15 mL polypropylene tubes and sent to Heidelberg Cement for analysis. ICP was carried out on an ICPE-9000 Shimadzu instrument in optical emission spectroscopy mode (ICP-OES).

In order to cross check the ICP results, the C—S—H samples were sent to XRF-Analytics Sàrl to be analyzed by X-Ray fluorescence spectroscopy (Optim'X 9900 Ceram XRF model). 20 g of hydrated sample were dried at 105 °C for 24 h and ignited at 950 °C for 1 h. 7.7 g of lithium tetraborate ($\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$) were added to the 0.7 g of the calcined sample to make a fused bead.

3. Reactor setup & operation

3.1. Batch reactor

The C—S—H was synthesized in a 12-cm diameter poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) reactor, based on the setup of Kumar et al. [7] (Figs. 1 and 2). The reactor lid has six slots for in-situ measurements, PMMA bars to increase turbulence and mixing inside the reactor, and glass inlet and outlet tubes for a gas purge. A polyvinyl chloride (PVC) tube is placed at the bottom of the glass inlet. Additionally, a 3-input y-shaped micromixer system with a spiral static mixer is included.

A Mettler Toledo InLab Expert Pro ISM-P67 pH electrode and a

Fig. 2. Picture of batch reactor, water bath, and magnetic stirrer for synthetic C—S—H synthesis.

Mettler Toledo perfectION Combination calcium electrode were used for in-situ measurements, collected on Mettler Toledo Easy Direct software. The reactor was placed in a bath and the temperature was regulated by a thermostat at 19 °C.

Solutions were introduced to the reactor by an ISMATEC REGLO-CPF Analog piston pump with an RH0.CTC pump head, and after synthesis, the precipitate was collected via a vacuum-filtration system on a 200 nm filter paper (Whatman ME 24/21 STL). Calcium nitrate tetrahydrate (Ca(NO₃)₂·4H₂O, CAS: 13477-34-4) and sodium metasilicate (Na₂SiO₃, CAS: 6834-92-0) were supplied from Sigma-Aldrich. NaOH pellets were supplied from Acros Organics (CAS: 1310-73-2), and ethanol was supplied from Reactolab S.A.

3.2. Solution preparation

Before synthesis, all parts of the apparatus were washed with deionized water and dried in a laminar flow hood. Piston pump tubes were purged with a solution of 50% ethanol, 50% pure water, and rinsed with a 50 mL solution of pure water before and after use. Ion electrodes and pH meters were stored in the respective storing solutions, calibrated twice before use, and washed with deionized water.

Solutions of calcium nitrate tetrahydrate, sodium metasilicate, and sodium hydroxide were prepared with decarbonated water. During and after preparation, the solutions were covered with a lid to avoid any contamination by dust. The solutions were stored for a maximum of two weeks before use.

4. Synthesis

4.1. Mix design

The Gibbs Energy Minimization Software or GEMS was used to simulate the relationship between Ca:Si ratio of synthetic C—S—H and pH as alkalis were added to the system. As the solubility of portlandite is inversely proportional to temperature, it is easier to avoid portlandite precipitation at lower temperatures. As a result, the temperature in all simulations was maintained at 19 °C. 100 mL of 0.224 M calcium nitrate tetrahydrate and 0.1 M sodium metasilicate were simulated at equilibrium with varying amounts of pH regulator, NaOH, as shown in Table 1 to achieve the listed target Ca:Si values.

4.2. Synthesis & drying

100 mL of 0.1 M sodium metasilicate solution was placed in the reactor with the required amount of 10 M NaOH for each Ca:Si ratio, as listed in Table 1. The batch reactor was placed in a thermostat-controlled water bath at a temperature of 19 °C to reduce the chance of portlandite formation. The reactor was then purged under a flow of nitrogen at 10 mL/min and mixed at 700 RPM for a minimum of 30 min to ensure even distribution of NaOH. Once the reactor reached the desired temperature, the mixing speed was increased to 1100 RPM, and 100 mL of 0.224 M calcium nitrate tetrahydrate solution was pumped into the reactor at a rate of 2 mL/min.

After a minimum of 3 h of reaction, the precipitate was taken out of

Table 1

: GEMS-predicted pH equilibrium values and required 10 M NaOH volume for target Ca:Si molar ratio in absence of Ca(OH)₂ and total reaction volume of 200 mL [22,23].

Target Ca:Si	pH (GEMS)	10 M NaOH (GEMS)
1	11.4	75 µL
1.25	11.9	675 µL
1.5	12.5	1.625 mL
1.75	12.9	3.475 mL
2	13.5	10 mL

the reactor and stored in suspension. To prepare a wet sample for analysis, the suspension was filtered and washed with a 1:1 pure water and ethanol solution. To dry, 25 g of a filtered and washed sample were placed in a -80 °C freezer for 24 h and freeze dried for an additional 24 h in an Alpha 1-2 LDplus freeze dryer operating at -50 °C and 0.01 mbar.

5. Results

5.1. Precipitate characterization: pure synthetic C—S—H

The X-ray diffractograms in Fig. 3 display the characteristic peaks of C—S—H at 29.4, 32.1, and 50.1 ± 0.1° 2θ for all C—S—H samples [24]. The diffractogram of the wet sample, immediately after filtration, exhibits a broad water peak. As C—S—H is poorly crystalline, the C—S—H peaks are still broad after drying but no secondary phases are observed.

All C—S—H, of both high and low Ca:Si, is susceptible to carbonation on exposure to air [7]. Fig. 4 shows the differential thermogravimetric (DTG) analysis of the same Ca:Si = 1.3 sample analyzed above. As for the XRD diffractogram, no portlandite is observed. The sample exhibits some decomposition due to the presence of carbonates, possibly both amorphous and crystalline, represented by the losses between 600 and 800 °C. Losses due to carbonation are observed in C—S—H samples both with and without the formation of portlandite, and can also be seen in Figs. 6 and 7.

5.1.1. Ca(OH)₂ formation in synthetic C—S—H

High Ca:Si C—S—H gives the same diffraction patterns as its lower Ca:Si counterpart. However, as the Ca:Si exceeds 1.5, portlandite formation is more often observed, affecting the actual Ca:Si of the C—S—H. Fig. 5 shows the diffraction patterns of two dried samples with target Ca:Si of 1.9. In the XRD of the second sample, portlandite peaks are observed.

In Fig. 6, thermogravimetric analysis of a nominal Ca:Si = 1.9 sample which exhibited portlandite peaks shows a decomposition from the presence of portlandite at 400 °C and carbonation around 600 °C. If the amount of portlandite measured by TGA is taken out of the overall mass, the recalculated Ca:Si of the C—S—H is 1.8 ± 0.1. If decomposition due to carbonation is also attributed to portlandite, the new adjusted Ca:Si becomes 1.73. ICP-OES analysis for this sample measured a Ca:Si of 1.79, suggesting that the majority of measured carbonation is of C—S—H itself and not of portlandite, and therefore does not affect the calculated Ca:Si of the C—S—H before carbonation. Fig. 7 shows the thermogravimetric analysis of a nominal Ca:Si = 1.9 sample which exhibited only losses due to carbonation.

Fig. 3. Filtered wet (gray) and freeze-dried (black) X-ray diffraction patterns of a pure C—S—H sample. C—S—H peaks are marked by, □. Ca:Si = 1.3.

Fig. 4. Differential thermogravimetric analysis (DTG) of pure C—S—H sample exhibiting losses due to carbonation between 600 and 800 °C, Ca:Si = 1.3.

Fig. 6. Differential thermogravimetric analysis (DTG) of impure C—S—H sample exhibiting losses due to the presence of portlandite at 400 °C and losses due to carbonation between 600 and 800 °C, nominal Ca:Si = 1.9.

Fig. 5. Pure (green) and impure (blue) C—S—H with nominal Ca:Si = 1.9. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

5.1.2. An overview of synthesized samples

The Ca:Si molar ratios of 46 samples from TGA analysis versus the target ratio are plotted in Fig. 8. The boxes in orange show recalculated Ca:Si values which account for both carbonation and portlandite decomposition peaks as sources of portlandite. The green boxes show the recalculated Ca:Si values, assuming that the portlandite peaks are the only source of portlandite in the samples. C—S—H at both high and low Ca:Si carbonates slightly in the TGA environment. As a result, the most accurate recalculated Ca:Si molar ratios can be represented by the green boxes. Pure, single-phase C—S—H was obtained at all nominal Ca:Si molar ratios, and the maximum pure Ca:Si produced was between 1.93 and 2. Of the samples plotted in Figs. 8, 60.8% were single-phase C—S—H, 23.9% of samples formed portlandite and have recalculated ratios within 2% of the nominal value.

Fig. 9 shows Ca:Si molar ratios, calculated from measurements of calcium and silicon in the precipitates with ICP and XRF. Lower Ca:Si molar ratios display a good correlation with the target ratios; however, at Ca:Si molar ratios of 1.8 and higher, the measured Ca:Si values are higher than the targeted ratios, most notably in samples with target

Fig. 7. Differential thermogravimetric analysis (DTG) of impure C—S—H sample exhibiting losses due to carbonation between 600 and 800 °C, nominal Ca:Si = 1.9.

ratios of 1.9 and higher, possibly due to adsorbed calcium at the surfaces that is not accounted for in the stoichiometric reaction as discussed in more detail below.

Three samples which showed no portlandite peaks by XRD, were analyzed by XRF, ICP, and TGA to determine how the experimental Ca:Si ratios compared to the target values. The results are displayed in Table 2.

The sample with the target Ca:Si of 1.95 exhibited slightly higher measured Ca:Si molar ratios in XRF and ICP while the lower Ca:Si samples show very close correlation with the targeted value. Overall, the results are consistent between the three methods within the expected error of the measurements.

5.1.3. Supernatant analysis

Comparison of supernatant analysis between GEMS and ICP shows that GEMS predicts a higher amount of calcium and sodium in the supernatant than measured empirically. At a nominal Ca:Si of 1.7, GEMS predicts a concentration of 3.8 mmol/L while only 0.39 mmol/L of calcium is measured. As the Ca:Si ratio increases, the discrepancy

Fig. 8. Plot of target Ca:Si molar ratios vs ratios from TGA analysis for 46C—S—H samples, based on decomposition due to portlandite only (green), and decomposition from portlandite + carbonated portlandite (orange). Green line represents target Ca:Si. Ranges within 1.5 of the interquartile range (IQR) are shown. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 9. Nominal Ca:Si molar ratios as measured by X-ray fluorescence (XRF) (orange) and inductively coupled plasma spectrometry (ICP-OES)(blue). Green line represents target Ca:Si. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Table 2

Comparison between target Ca:Si molar ratio and Ca:Si molar ratios measured by XRF, ICP, and TGA (Ca:Si ± 0.1) with portlandite (CH) and carbonates (Cc). An average error of all experimental data with respect to each target ratio is given.

Target	XRF	ICP	TGA with CH	TGA with CH & Cc	Avg % error
1.19	1.18	1.16	1.19	1.17	1.26%
1.35	1.34	1.34	1.35	1.33	0.74%
1.95	1.99	2.05	1.95	1.93	2.05%

between GEMS calculations and measurements increases.

At a nominal Ca:Si of 2.0, GEMS predicts a concentration of 23.3 mmol/L to be compared with the measured value of 0.69 mmol/L of

calcium (Fig. 10). These results suggest that there could be an adsorption of calcium on the surface of the C—S—H, and that the amount of adsorption increases with increasing Ca:Si. This is consistent with the higher Ca:Si ratios observed in the ICP-XRF data in Table 2 and Fig. 9 and the lower concentrations of calcium measured in the supernatants. The amount of calcium adsorbed seems to be closely related to the Ca/Si ratio.

Similarly, GEMS predicts a silicon concentration that is significantly lower than the measured value in the supernatant samples over the full range of Ca:Si molar ratios. GEMS calculates silicon concentrations between 0.0005 and 0.02 mmol/L. Measured concentrations range between 0.05 and 0.06 mmol/L.

Some discrepancy between GEMS and measured concentrations is expected as GEMS provides equilibrium values and does not factor surface complexation into the calculations [22,23]. Additionally, the lower amounts of calcium and sodium in the supernatant are coherent with the higher amounts of calcium measured in the precipitates, suggest that as the Ca:Si molar ratio increases, the adsorption of calcium and sodium on the surface of C—S—H also increases. Interfacial concentration profiles such as those predicted by Labbez et al. [26] would be needed to further evaluate this proposed adsorption phenomena, but are outside the scope of this manuscript.

5.2. Supersaturation condition

The precipitation of C—S—H is a thermodynamically driven process, and the preferential formation of high Ca:Si C—S—H over portlandite can be understood by comparing the supersaturation ratios of the two hydration products as the reaction proceeds.

The supersaturation ratio compares the activity products of ions composing a phase at a current state versus the liquid-solid equilibrium state [27]. When the ratio is above one, the component, *i*, is supersaturated in the media and has a higher chance to precipitate.

Eq. (1) shows the supersaturation index where *S* is saturation ratio of component *i*, α_i is activity of component *i*, *T* is temperature, *P* is pressure, and * represents the equilibrium state.

$$S_i = \frac{\alpha_i(T, P_0)}{\alpha_i^*(T, P_0)} \quad (1)$$

Saturation indices of C—S—H and portlandite were calculated for the described synthetic C—S—H recipes with the population balance model of Andalibi et al. [21,28]. For Ca:Si ratios of 2 and 1.75, the saturation indices of C—S—H are above 1 throughout the reaction. Meanwhile the indices of portlandite are below 1, which remains undersaturated throughout.

The well-mixed system favors C—S—H precipitation without the precipitation of a second phase. Not only is the C—S—H saturation index 8 to 10 times higher than the saturation index of portlandite, but also the saturation index of portlandite never reaches 1 and portlandite is always soluble in the media (Fig. 11).

In previous experiments to synthesize C—S—H, the Ca:Si ratio plateaus at 1.5 as Portlandite becomes supersaturated [5]. In an uncontrolled environment, there is competition between portlandite and C—S—H formation because high Ca:Si C—S—H forms only in high pH environments, ~12.4 and above, as portlandite is less soluble as the pH increases [7]. As a result, in a poorly mixed system, or in a system in which the calcium solution is added too quickly to the reactor higher concentrations of hydroxide ions may occur locally, increasing the chance for portlandite formation in conjunction with C—S—H.

In a synthetic system in which the initial concentrations are controlled to create supersaturation conditions for C—S—H, and in a system in which the reactants are added at the correct rate and the total reactor volume is small enough and well designed to ensure proper mixing, the preferential precipitation of C—S—H and C—S—H alone can be assured.

Fig. 10. Silicon (green) and calcium (blue) concentrations in supernatants, GEMS-calculated & measured (ICP-OES). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 11. Saturation indices for synthetic C—S—H (black) and portlandite (red) Ca:Si = 1.75 and 2, calculated with the population balance model. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

6. C—S—H filtering, storage & handling

6.1. Filtering & collection

After a minimum of 3 h of reaction, the precipitate was removed from the reactor and stored in suspension or collected through vacuum filtration. The suspension is filtered until 100 mL remains unfiltered. The suspension is then washed with 60 mL 1:1 pure water and ethanol solution, and filtered again until the C—S—H has a wet paste consistency.

To prevent the formation of portlandite during vacuum filtration, enough supernatant is kept in the sample to prevent the compact cracking, effectively keeping the precipitate in an equilibrium. Similarly, when precipitates are not filtered for long enough and form a soupy paste, the C—S—H is more prone to carbonation.

6.2. Storage and handling

Synthetic C—S—H can be stored both wet and dry. For stability,

samples are best kept as sealed suspensions. If precipitated in accordance to the protocol, synthetic C—S—H will not form any additional or undesired phases in equilibrium with the reaction liquor, and will remain in equilibrium.

High Ca:Si samples show stability after one year in storage; though samples carbonate when exposed to ambient conditions for only 30 min, as seen in Fig. 12.

Drying more than the suggested 25 g of filtered sample can lead to damp samples, which will carbonate after a shorter period of time in storage. Storage in an airtight container and a sealed bag is most appropriate to prevent carbonation and portlandite formation of dried samples, as seen in Fig. 13.

Samples that show the presence of portlandite are more susceptible to carbonation and the formation of more portlandite. However, when sealed completely, more portlandite does not form.

Fig. 12. XRD diffraction patterns for wet, filtered C—S—H, Ca:Si = 1.9 at 1 week (orange) 1 year (dark blue), and 1 year after 30 min exposure to ambient environment (light blue). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 13. Longevity analysis of 1 month old (green) and 3-month-old (blue) impure samples with different degrees of sealing. Figure a corresponds to a sample exhibiting small amounts of portlandite sealed completely in a Polyethylene tube and bag. Figure b corresponds to a sample kept in a polyethylene tube. Both samples show increased carbonation and the non-bagged sample shows increase in portlandite peaks. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

7. Conclusions

The objective of this paper is to provide guidelines for the synthesis of pure, single-phase C—S—H at both low and high Ca:Si molar ratios that range from 1 to 2. Careful control of temperature and mixing is required to maintain supersaturation conditions for C—S—H while simultaneously suppressing the supersaturation of portlandite, and synthesizing pure, single-phase products. Additionally, thorough cleaning and preparation are imperative to avoid creating sites for nucleation due to dust particles or other impurities.

The synthesis step, however, is not the only factor that must be controlled in producing single-phase C—S—H. Samples may be synthesized without secondary phases, but can form $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ or CaCO_3 in the drying, handling, or storage steps.

When comparing the measured concentrations of calcium and silicon in the precipitates and the corresponding supernatants, a significant amount of calcium from the supernatant appears to be adsorbed on the precipitate which may be attributed to surface interactions, particularly on high Ca:Si C—S—H. Further investigations are needed in future work to better understand these phenomena.

In summary, this paper provides a reliable method for the production of both low and high Ca:Si ratio synthetic C—S—H. The paper highlights where care has to be taken both in the precipitation method and on

consequent handling to allow reproducible synthesis of synthetic C—S—H with a desired Ca:Si ratio.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Maya Harris: Methodology, Software, Validation, Investigation, Writing – original draft. **Grace Simpson:** Methodology, Investigation. **Karen Scrivener:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Paul Bowen:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors have no affiliation with any organization with a direct or indirect financial interest in the subject matter discussed in the manuscript.

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